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TYPICAL PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL FINDINGS IN TUBERCULOUS SPONDYLITIS AND EXPRESSION OUTCOMES OF IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL MARKERS CD45 AND KI-67

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Abstract: This article presents findings derived from the pathomorphological examination of surgical histological specimens from patients diagnosed with tuberculous spondylitis. The study emphasizes the specific morphological features of the disease and evaluates the expression levels of the immunohistochemical markers CD45 and Ki-67.

Aim of the Study: To identify pathomorphological alterations in bone tissue and to assess the immunohistochemical expression of CD45 and Ki-67 markers in patients with tuberculous spondylitis.

Materials and Methods: The research was conducted on histological samples prepared from bone tissue of 18 patients of varying age and gender diagnosed with tuberculous spondylitis. Hematoxylin-eosin and Van Gieson staining techniques were applied to examine general histological and histochemical features typical of the condition. Additionally, the expression levels of CD45 and Ki-67 markers were assessed immunohistochemically.

Paraffin blocks prepared from the patients' bone tissues were used for immunohistochemical analysis. Sections 2–4 µm thick were cut using a microtome, mounted on glass slides coated with poly-L-lysine, and processed for staining. The tissue samples underwent dehydration and dewaxing via the avidin-biotin-immunoperoxidase method, antigen retrieval using the Ventana Benchmark XT system, and antibody staining with an automated Roche Special System (Switzerland).

The analysis revealed a high frequency of immunopositive cells expressing CD45 and Ki-67, indicating active cellular processes. Digital imaging and interpretation were performed using QuPath-0.4.0 and NanoZoomer Digital Pathology platforms.

The expression levels of Ki-67 (proliferation index) and CD45 were quantified as a percentage of positively stained cells and categorized into the following groups: 0 (no staining), 1+ (<20% of cells, weak expression), 2+ (20–60% of cells, moderate expression), and 3+ (>60% of cells, strong expression).

Keywords: Tuberculosis, spondylitis, marker, immunohistochemistry, spine, biopsy.

Main Part: Tuberculous spondylitis, also known as vertebral tuberculosis, represents a specific infectious lesion of the spine caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. This pathology is characterized by the formation of granulomas, which progressively affect bone tissue, leading to the destruction and deformation of vertebral structures.

Pathomorphological examination and microscopic analysis of operative and biopsy specimens revealed the presence of granulomas typical of tuberculosis in the majority of bone tissue samples. These granulomas exhibited central zones of necrosis surrounded by lymphohistiocytic infiltration, epithelioid cells, and multinucleated Pirogov–Langhans giant cells. The nuclei of these giant cells were arranged peripherally, and in some areas, diffusely scattered. Additionally, leukocytic infiltrates were observed (see Figure 1).

It was also established that in the center of the inflammatory focus, the bone lamellae underwent significant destruction and resorption. The structural integrity of bone tissue in these areas was severely compromised. At the periphery, the boundaries of the remaining bone plates appeared blurred and fragmented into fine particles. The lamellae were notably thinned, with internal erosions, and the bone lacunae showed signs of compaction and proximity to each other, reflecting advanced degenerative and inflammatory changes.

Figure 1. Tuberculous spondylitis. Hemotoxic eosin stained magnified 200 times. Specific granuloma characteristic of tuberculosis is identified in the given micropreparation (1). In the center of the granuloma, caseous necrosis and epithelioid cells and large Piragov Langhans cells with numerous nuclei are detected in the peripheral part. In the peripheral part, the bone plate is partially preserved, it is thinned and resorption processes are increased in the part of the preserved bone plate (2). The walls of blood vessels become thinner and signs of fullness appear. Sclerc, degenerative changes are detected around the granuloma.

In certain areas of the tissue, osteocyte cells were absent. In other regions, the accumulation of osteoclasts along the walls of partially preserved bone lamellae was observed, indicating enhanced bone resorption activity. In some peripheral zones of the remaining bone plates, hyperplasia of osteoblasts was noted, suggesting reactive bone formation.

Histological examination also revealed the absence of some osteonal canals, while vascular structures demonstrated signs of congestion, and localized foci of hemosiderosis were present in specific areas. A noticeable increase in the number of mesenchymal cells was identified, with evidence of infiltrative tumor-like formations among them.

Moreover, the amount of collagen fibers was markedly elevated in the regions of bone destruction, particularly around the walls of blood vessels (see Fig. 2). Degenerative changes were prominent in the affected bone tissue: cellular elements and fibrous structures showed signs of disorganized proliferation. At the interface between the damaged and intact tissue, collagen fibers and other stromal components accumulated densely, forming areas encapsulated by sclerotic changes and fibrous capsule-like structures.

Figure 2. Tuberculous spondylitis. Magnified 200 times, stained by the Van Gizon method. Bone plates are eroded, thinned and separated into separate parts, their lacunae become denser and remain. In the destroyed bone tissue, fibrous structures are rough, coarse, disorderly. The amount of thin and fine collagen has increased in the walls of blood vessels.

The expression level of the immunohistochemical marker Ki-67 in cases of tuberculous spondylitis was investigated. The Ki-67 marker serves as an indicator of cellular proliferative activity and is commonly utilized in the assessment of proliferative processes, including those associated with tumor growth. Its expression is quantified as a percentage, reflecting the proportion of actively dividing cells and thereby indicating the intensity of cellular proliferation.

Ki-67 is a nuclear protein that is specifically expressed during active phases of the cell cycle (G1, S, G2, and mitosis), but not in resting (G0) cells, making it a reliable marker for identifying proliferating cells. As such, it plays a critical role in the evaluation of tissue regeneration and pathological cell turnover.

Total number of cells detected	898
Positive cells	474
Negative Cells	424
Positive Expression	52,7 %
General area	1046397 px ²

Figure 3: Expression of Ki 67 marker in bone tissue of patients with tuberculous spondylitis. Stained by DAB chromogenic method. The image is magnified 200 times. (QuPath-0.4.0, software evaluation. Cells with positive expression are in red) Positive expression 52,7%

Total number of cells detected	637
Positive cells	371
Negative Cells	266
Positive Expression	58,24 %
General area	1035300 px ²

Figure 4: Expression of Ki 67 marker in bone tissue of patients with tuberculous spondylitis. Stained by DAB chromogenic method. The image is magnified 200 times. (QuPath-0.4.0, software evaluation. Cells with positive expression are in red) Positive expression 58,24%

The expression levels of the Ki-67 marker were evaluated using immunohistochemical analysis of bone tissue specimens obtained from patients with tuberculous spondylitis. The findings demonstrated positive expression ranging from 47% to 57%, corresponding to a moderate expression level, or 2+ according to the standard immunohistochemical grading scale. The average proliferative index was calculated at 52% (2+). The observed cellular proliferation was predominantly attributed to mesenchymal cells located around the inflammatory foci, as well as to osteoclasts and, to a lesser extent, osteoblasts (see Figs. 3, 4).

The expression profile of the immunohistochemical marker CD45 in tuberculous spondylitis was also assessed. CD45, also known as leukocyte common antigen, is a transmembrane protein expressed on the surface of all leukocytes. This marker is present on various hematopoietic and immune system cells, including B-lymphocytes, T-lymphocytes, natural killer (NK) cells, monocytes, and granulocytes.

CD45 plays a critical role in immune cell activation and differentiation during maturation. It is widely used in immunopathological diagnostics to distinguish between T- and B-cell lineages in hematological and immune-related conditions. Expression of CD45 increases progressively from immature hematopoietic precursors to fully differentiated immune cells, with the highest expression levels observed in mature lymphocytes.

Moreover, CD45 exists in several isoforms that are differentially expressed depending on the cell type and maturation stage. For example, the CD45RO isoform

is predominantly expressed on memory T lymphocytes, aiding in their identification and functional classification in immune responses.

Figure 5. Expression of CD 45 marker in bone tissue infected with tuberculous spondylitis.

Stained by DAB chromogenic method. The image is magnified 200 times. Positive expression 23%

Immunohistochemical analysis of bone tissue samples from patients with tuberculous spondylitis revealed varying levels of CD45 marker expression. In two specimens, CD45 demonstrated a positive expression level of 16%, corresponding to a mild expression score (1+). In the remaining samples, expression levels ranged from 22% to 31.8%, indicative of moderate positivity (2+). Thus, the average level of leukocytic infiltrate was approximately 27%, classified as 2+.

The leukocytic infiltrate was predominantly localized in the form of focal accumulations around granulomatous structures, highlighting its association with the immune response in the inflammatory microenvironment.

Conclusion:

Based on the findings from our study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Macroscopic Examination: Macroscopic analysis frequently revealed greater damage to the cancellous substance of the vertebral body, with relatively less involvement of the vertebral arch and outgrowths. The pathological process was observed to extend along the surface of the spine (anteriorly, laterally, and posteriorly), as well as across vertebrae via the intervertebral discs. This suggests the potential formation of intervertebral abscesses in patients, with the disease process

potentially spreading in both upward and downward directions. Lateral spread could lead to the formation of paravertebral abscesses, while posterior extension may compress the spinal cord, resulting in neurological deficits such as paralysis. In some cases, cold abscesses or fistulas were detected within the focus of the lesion.

2. Pathomorphological Findings: From a pathomorphological standpoint, the study identified characteristic granulomas associated with tuberculosis, including central caseous necrosis within the granulomas, surrounded by epithelioid cells and large multinucleated Pirogov-Langhans giant cells. The investigation revealed significant destruction of bone plates in the center of the inflammatory foci, with these plates being broken, liquefied, and resorbed. Peripheral bone plates, although preserved, were fragmented and thinned, with an increase in resorption activity. Additionally, thinning of blood vessel walls, characteristic hyperemia, and focal hemosiderosis were observed in certain regions of the tissue.

3. Histochemical Observations: Histochemical analysis confirmed the presence of degenerative processes involving cellular proliferation and the disorganized arrangement of fibrous structures within the damaged bone tissue. Collagen fibers appeared dense, thickened, and irregularly arranged, particularly at the junction between the inflamed and healthy tissue areas. These findings highlight the ongoing fibrotic changes and the tissue's response to the chronic inflammatory process.

4. Immunohistochemical Analysis: Immunohistochemical analysis of the CD45 marker revealed an average expression level of 27% (2+), indicating moderate involvement of immune cells in the inflammatory response associated with tuberculous spondylitis. The expression level of the Ki-67 marker in bone tissue averaged 52% (2+), suggesting significant proliferative activity. This proliferation was primarily attributed to mesenchymal and osteoclast cells, with a lesser contribution from osteoblasts. The heightened proliferative activity supports the notion that increased bone resorption and the formation of fibrous tissue are central to the pathogenesis of the disease.

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